

A STUDY ON THE LIFE OF ADOLESCENCE IN THE PRESENT DAY SCENARIO

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Abstract:

The first sentence that comes to the investigator whenever she thinks about adolescent is - it is a time of "storm and stress". Very few may not face the changes. But a majority of the teenagers have to face a lot of psychological, sociological and physical challenges. Of these some may be real and some may be imaginary. Religious teachings, friends, brothers and sisters, relatives, financial problems all these can be the causes for the hassles. Bossing friends, parent's absence and lack of time, loneliness, lack of good friends etc. can become very taxing in a teenager's life. The absence of people at home due to the breaking up of joint family system, the women's job outside the local area are all new and unexpected challenges a young girl or boy has to confront and tackle successfully. The researcher would like to make a study about reasons for the present day challenges of teenagers and give suggestions for creating a healthy environment for the maximum development of a teenager in the 21st century.

Index Terms: Taxing, Tackle, Confront, Storm and Stress & Challenges

Introduction:

The word adolescence means the age between 12 and 20. These 7 years are very important in every human life. The basic formative period is up to six years. Every individual will be hampered or set up in this period. Proper positive stimulation and good experience will be a positive push to the future. After this the adolescent period is very important. If a child gets good experience from the parents and society it will lead to a successful life till his last breath. Our epics Mahabharatha and Ramayana are all symbolic to represent human life.

Vibhandakamaharshi had a son Rishyasinga Muni. No other period of life is described as detailed as adolescence. Vibhandaka was so particular that his son should not have any female contact. He made all arrangements for that when Vyshali came to his hermitage he was seeing a female for the first time. His immature behaviour produced lot of complications. He was abducted by Vyshali to her king. Rishyasinga had a power to bring rain and the king achieved success. This story is pointing out the immature behaviour pattern of Rishyasinga due to lack of contact with females guided by mature and elderly people. During adolescence healthy and proper mixing with opposite sex will mature a person. Males and females are not separate compartments. They are complementary –with guidance of old and mature people the mixing of opposite sex is a must for the positive development. Before adolescence, that is childhood is the formative period of brain. That will enable him or her to receive proper information data in adolescence. This will enhance a person to utilise this data for creative functions. This dynamic bio-functioning prepare a person to higher degree of creative achievements. Feeding data in adolescent period is very important. All these data must be input in an adolescent in a very selective manner and with proper discrimination. These are the dynamic school from which everything will be formulated. The age of an adolescent is a turbulent state of life. If utmost care is not taken sexually they are polluted and that will create deep guilt feeling in adolescent and that will be a great impediment in his progress. Proper and intelligent sex education is a must in this period. Mature persons like parents, teachers or elders can do proper guidance. If they

will be given this knowledge from their colleagues that may hamper their life. The great philosopher Will Durant imparted all sex knowledge to his only daughter and she became a very mature person. Like ordinary events and knowledge he provided this knowledge to his daughter and she became a very mature person. Sexuality is one of the important factors in life. It is connected with propagation of life. A healthy race will arise from a healthy mind.

In itself sex is nothing. It must be used as a tool of companionship and sharing. This companionship and sharing will make a man or woman mature and perfect. In animal, sex is only a biological instinct and process. After the biological process personal intimacy and sharing is very rare. But in man this biological bond permeates into his very existence. It channelizes it to the development of his personality. In summum bonum sex is a must for the propagation at the same time it must be tallied with other personal development and relationship. The ancient learned persons of India intelligently divided the whole life into four units. They declared it as four ashrams. It is called chaturashrams. They are Brahmachari - Grahastha, Vanaprastha and Bhikshu. According to Buddha last stage is Nirvana stage - This Buddha acquired in his last stage of life. Brahmacharya is for adolescent person. That time he resided with his Guru and served his Guru and his wife. He did all the domestic work for his Guru and his wife. After that rigorous training in different branches of knowledge was imparted, language ability logical ability grammar ability, knowledge in Jyotisha (Astrology) etc. were acquired during this period. Debates also were conducted in the presence of Guru. So their adolescent life was disciplined and dynamically projected to higher projectiles of life.

At this adolescent stage he controlled all the erotic thoughts and channelized it into the concentration of God. "Brahmanivicharam Brahmacharyam". It is the period of meditation in the supreme, concentration practicing, all yoga disciplines and yogasanas. It is the period of through education and service. Through the service of Guru they acquired humility and service mind. The supreme channelization of adolescence produced wonderful persons in the ancient times. Training of adolescence is considered as a very important factor in life. Nature of enquiry and curiosity will develop maximum in the period of adolescence. This period must be satisfied with at most caution and care, otherwise it will hamper a person. Einstein was considered as an idiot and dull witted person by his teacher in his adolescent stage. But his uncle taught him Euclid geometry and he became very intelligent and efficient. This led to the finding of atomic bomb without a laboratory. He found $E=MC^2$ by using paper and pencil. This Euclid geometry was a great stimulus for his intellectual development.

The story of Uthalaka and his son Nachikethas gives a good example for this. When Nachikethas was an adolescent Uthalaka conducted a great sacrifice otherwise great yaga. At the end of this sacrifice he donated cows to the Brahmans, among these cows some were not with teeth. By seeing this Nachikethas became agitated and retorted to his father and asked him why are you giving such cows to Brahmans. Uthalaka got in this angry mood of his father Nachikethas told his father instead of toothless cows why cannot you give me to the Brahmans. The angry father replied to his son "I am going to donate you to Lord "Kala" (God of time) this means death. After that Uthalaka subsided his emotion. Uthalaka told his son "I am sorry". In order to make his father's wording Nachikethas straight went to Yamaloka. When he reached there he saluted yama and told him to receive him in Yamaloka. But yama categorically denied and replied. Nobody dare to come over here like you, but I go to them and tied them with rope and bring them here. When the time will come I will come and bring you here.

Then Nachikethas replied I must fulfil the word of my father. By seeing his determination and devotion mentally Yama was moved and asked him to receive a boon from him. Yama promised to give empires, thousands of beautiful ladies playing musical instruments. He asked him to receive this boon and enjoy it for thousands of years. Then Nachikethas counter argued "will this enjoyment last forever. Then Yama replied in the material world everything has an end. That is the divine decision that nobody can change. Yama asked him "to take any other boon from me". Then Nachikethas asked what is the stage after death. Then yama retorted that great scholars have no idea about this. Then Yama gave him this answer

"Athmanamrathinamvithi Shareeram Rathaveva cha
Buddhimthumsarathi Manapragrahamevacha
Indriyanihayanahruvishayamtheshugochaetc.....

This soul is the proprietor of the chariot and this body is the chariot itself. Intellect (Buddhi) is the driver, the mind is the saddle. The five senses are the vicious horses which ferociously is eager to satisfy all desires. So you must direct your intellect to control the saddle and direct your intellect to supreme lord instead of stepping into desires and direct to supreme Lord. Yama's advice helped the boy to go in the proper path. This is very good example of directing adolescent enquiry in the proper path. This is the beginning of Kadopanidhat. All these stories are symbolic. It shows that adolescent stage must be properly directed. Adolescence is the adding stage of experience. The future drama is acted on this stage of experience. Arranged and well formulated experiences help a person to function well in the later stage of life. Hampered formula will hamper the good life in the future. This adding and formulation of experience must be guided by mature persons. Misdirection in this stage will hamper the personality a lot. A teacher is a great guide and help to the student in education system. Likewise guidance of a mature teacher is essential in adolescent stage. In adolescent life many opinions and advice from different persons of different strata may come. All these advices and guidance may sometimes collide and adolescent will be confused. So a good teacher is highly essential to give guide line as to what should be selected and what should be rejected. So he should develop the capacity of the legendary swan which can differentiate water and milk. In the life of an adolescent like other stages of life he must pass through many ups and downs. By using the steer of discretion and discrimination he must go on the path of life with utmost care and plan. The stage of adolescent period in all animals especially homosapiens is very important period. They are getting experiences from their parents or cooperative elders enough experience to face different situations in life.

Among the pride of lions adolescent lions are getting hunting experience of speed precision and exact act. Timing is also very important in hunting. They are well trained and that will make their life easy without great impediments. In elephants adolescent elephant gets training for social movement. The hierarchy will be established at this stage and this hierarchy will change according to the proven abilities. Man is a social animal. So social interactions are highly inevitable for their success and achievement. Very ancient time man lived as tribes. There were many taboos and inhibition and promotion. So adolescent life of tribes are so important in grouping and formation. According to this they adjusted and adapted for any situation to confront with. So they were able to live a healthy life. According to the evolution of society the social pattern also developed and became a developed society. So these evolutions made different kingdoms, different languages and different methods of administration. We can see all these things from the Roman history. When they were confronted with

certain nomadic tribes they grouped together to resist. When their ladies were abducted by these nomadic tribes the gravity of the situation increased. These village people grouped under Ceaser and conquered all the nomadic tribes and their lands. In such a way Roman empire was established. Pax Romana Roman peace was established that time in the known world. They formulated Canon law for administration. Court and judiciary were established. All these occurred due to the experience of their life. Adolescent experience pressurised them to act. That caused the modern civilised world adolescent. Later these Romans attacked England and subdued the very ferocious and war like Anglo Saxons. All these Anglo Saxons were disciplined and that nation became a well civilised country.

Buddha changed this world in a great esteem of culture. In his adolescent stage of life Buddha experienced many trials and tribulations-and that caused him to reject the mundane world and he became an ascetic. Through his search he found many moral values and principles. If man lives only to satisfy his carnal desires it will lead him to infinite varieties of sorrows. So he must control his passions and desires and live a good life. He advocated Vegetarianism. He advised that the stomach of a man should not be a burial ground for animals. After Kalinga war even though Asoka completely succeeded the tragedies of war produced in Asoka great agony. He was immersed in a sea of sorrow. He wept and wept .At last he embraced Buddhism. Due to his royal influence it spread all over the world. Asoka was a great man. Circumstances made him a war monk. In his adolescent stage he loved the beautiful princess of Kalinga. According to the so called caste system Asoka's late Mauriyanancesters were not pure Kshatriyas. One of his ancestor parents married a low caste lady while he was in war fare race. Then Asoka forwarded his desire to this princess of Kalinga and she rejected it. Asoka took it as a racial discrimination. The terrible Kalinga war happened. Thousands and thousands of people were slaughtered. There is saying that Dayanadi in Kalinga was turned into red due to the bloodshed. Kalinga princess had adopted Buddhism in her adolescent life. She dedicated her life for the Ultimate state *i.e.* Nirvana. So she rejected the persuasion of Asoka. In Buddhism there is no caste system. All men are created equal. This is the principle of Buddhism. Asoka mistook this and Kalinga war occurred. Later he understood that it is due to his misunderstanding. So he embraced the princess religion Buddhism and he spread it all over the world.

I described all these things to show that adolescent's experience in life create lot of consequences. Everything is formulated in adolescence. In the Bible it is said that Christ disappeared at the age of 12 and he appeared only at the age of 30. It shows that this adolescent period of Christ created a lot of impact in him and that impact created in the world a great religious, cultural and social revolution. At the time of Christ and before also certain Buddhist monks established an ashram in the bank of Jordan River. The adolescent searching spirit of Christ led him to their ashram'. He conversed with them and he went to India at his adolescent stage. He studied religious Buddhism and Magic from Hindu saints. After studying many things he returned to his native place and he started to teach the new religion which taught all men are equal, and their father is God. Union with father only give peace and freedom to soul. 12 persons became his disciples under leadership of Christ St. Peter was first among them. All these people were very common uneducated persons without any learning. Christ came to the world. History was divided into before and after Christ. His adolescent influence created all these things.

In his childhood and adolescent stage Puthalibhai the mother of Mahatma Gandhi read Ramayana to Mohandas Karamchand Gandhi. All the high principles of Ramayana

influenced Gandhi to a great extent. All the morals, principles and ethics formulated in him by hearing Ramayana. This strength enabled him to become a great leader. Through the moral and noble fighting of Sathyagraha he liberated India from the slavery of British people. When he was shot by Nathuram Godsay Gandhi repeated the Lords name Hi Ram Hi Ram with bleeding heart. His adolescent experiences made him a great leader that the world has ever seen before. Albert Einstein said such a leader never came to this planet. Educational pattern for adolescence is very important. Small classes are very good for them. With a small group of students a teacher can give full attention to each student. It gives him proper input for his studies. All his misbehaviour can be corrected, such as lack of attention and listening, laziness, distraction, lack of concentration etc. can be corrected easily in a small group are different psychological and mental problems in adolescent age. Autism, truancy, irritating behaviour etc. These can be corrected by counselling, psychoanalysis and proper medication.

In Ayurveda there are certain herbs and medicines which will correct many mental problems. To promote intellect use of Brahmi (centellaasiatica), Mandukaparni (Indian Peneear plant) Powder of white flowered Sankupushpa (clitoriaternatealin), Brahmikritha, Saraswatharista are excellent medicine for correcting mental disabilities and promote higher intellectual ability. Sudden changes in the usual behavioural and learning patterns are particularly significant and should be investigated. Sudden changes in a student which is good or bad must be corrected promptly and direct him in a positive way. It is highly essential for his progress in study and in life. Early detection of misbehaviour pattern must be studied and corrected for prevention of future disorders. In adolescence the onset of sexual desires and turbulence create lot of problems. This must be corrected properly. In conclusion we can say adolescent stage of life is wonderful, marvellous, beautiful, charming, dynamic and hopeful stage of life. These impulses must be properly triggered and directed by mature elders to enhance him to higher achievement in life.

References

1. Alfred M. Freeman, M.D. and Harold I. Kaplan M.D. (1967) Comprehensive Text Book of Psychiatry. The Williams and Wilkins Company, Baltimore.
2. Alexander M. D & France G. M & Sheldon T. Selesnick M. D. (1968). History of Psychiatry, New American Library.
3. A.P.J. Abdul Kalam with Sivathanu Pillai (2004). Tata McGrow Hill Company, Delhi, India.
4. Dr. Nazeer Ahammad (2011) The Quran, Publishers, The American Institute of Islamic History and Culture 1160 Ridgemont Place Concord U.S.A
5. Goswami C. L., Shastri, Srimath Bhagavata Mahapurana (2010) Part 1 and part 11 GITA Press. Gorakhpur
6. Islamic History and Culture 1160 Ridgemont Place Concord U.S.A.
7. Indian Medicinal Plants (1944). Orient Longman Hyderabad (A. P.) James C. Coleman D.B. (1976). Taraporevala Sons and company Private Ltd. Bombay.
8. Jawaharlal Nehru (2010) (First published in 1940) Penguin Group (U.S.A) New York.
9. Ramesh Menon (2009). Rupa, Co-Printed in India by Rekha Printers, PVT Ltd, New Delhi.
10. Swami Vivekananda (1989). Swapna Printing works, Private Limited, Calcutta, India.
11. Vettem Mani (2006). Puranic Encyclopedia, Current Books .D.C Press Ltd, Kottayam, Kerala.